

Table S1: We used the algorithm Maxent implemented in the R package Wallace (Kass et al., 2018) to estimate the resistance matrices for the ecological connectivity estimation. 10,000 background points were randomly generated inside a minimum convex polygon of each species. To reduce sampling bias, geographic coordinates were spatially thinned using the R package sptin (Aiello-Lammens et al., 2015), applying a thinning distance of 5 km. We partition occurrences with the the 'block' geographical partition scheme of ENMEVAL. After removing highly correlated Bioclim variables, we ended using: "bio02", 'bio03', 'bio08', 'bio13', 'bio14', 'bio15', 'bio18', 'bio19' for all species. We evaluated three feature classes (L, LQ, H) with ENMEVAL (Muscarella et al., 2014). Models with lowest corrected Akaike Information Criterion were selected.

The wallace session codes (executable R script) for all species included in the analysis are attached in the supplementary materials, so any person can replicate the species distribution models and their parameters.